

Title: Digital Twin pipeline: An open and collaborative Knowledge Management System for Digital Twin implementation, benchmark and design

Abstract: Nowadays, Industry 4.0 faces challenges regarding the implementation of digital solutions that connect the physical and digital worlds. With the growing open innovation initiatives, open knowledge sharing appears to be an interesting lever for connecting actors facing similar challenges and supporting the dissemination of technical solutions tailored to the actors' context. This article proposes an open and collaborative knowledge management system. Its purpose is to enable industrial and academic actors to document, share, find, and discover new end-to-end solutions that connect the physical world to the digital world, thereby operationalizing the concept of Digital Twins. The article begins with a background section on digital twin tools and knowledge management. Then, a benchmark is conducted on community-based knowledge sharing platforms related to digital twin solutions. No platform met the assessment criteria. This result leads to the article's proposition: an open and collaborative knowledge management system for Digital Twin end-to-end solutions. The proposed platform is powered by an open CMS/wiki, and its use is illustrated with an academic end-to-end Digital Twin solution. The article concludes with discussions on theoretical and operational aspects of the documentation process, limitations of the proposition, and future work.

1 Introduction

The digital transformation is a systemic revolution [1,2]. In the industry, it has revolutionized the ways of designing and producing goods and services, utilizing computer-aided design (CAD) and knowledge management (KM) tools, as well as automated production systems [3]. Worldwide digital connectivity has further led to the Industry 4.0 paradigm [3]. One of the concepts emerging from this new paradigm is the digital twin (DT). The concept of DT is often attributed to Grieves in 2002 [4], and its definition has been the subject of dedicated research [5,6]. In this article, the use of the DT concept aligns with the definition by Semeraro et al. [6]. A DT aims to provide an accurate real-time visualization of the Physical Twin (PT) and to enable instantaneous feedback on the PT from the DT interfaces, either automatically or with human-in-the-loop control. The DT concept aims to leverage the digital automation revolution for the management of physical assets. Indeed, many processes can be significantly improved by digital services, such as maintenance, production planning, and product development.

Twinning requires technologies that communicate and analyze data between the physical and virtual domains. The Internet of Things (IoT), cyber-physical systems, artificial intelligence, and cloud computing have been identified as the primary technological components of the DT paradigm [7,8]. Data communication is possible through sequences of integrated hardware and software components. In this article, the concept of DT pipeline (DTp) is introduced to refer to such sequences of components. To summarize, a DTp can be defined as a sequence of integrated hardware and software components that can communicate data from physical to virtual (P2V), from virtual to physical (V2P), or from virtual to virtual (V2V).

However, DT implementation still faces challenges in the industry [9]. The main challenges include the use of expensive technologies, the need for multiple areas of expertise, and a lack of standardization regarding design frameworks, architectures, modeling, performance measurement, and connectivity between components. One critical step in DT implementation is the P2V connection. In this article, this step is referred to as the physical-to-virtual digital twin pipeline (P2V DTp) implementation, which encompasses data acquisition and physical data processing. Most of the following DT processes rely on the quality of the acquired physical data, *e.g.* simulation or decision-making. The P2V DTp implementation faces the same previously identified challenges [9,10]. Therefore, this article specifically focuses on the P2V DTp implementation.

Moreover, the digital transformation came with the information age and the open innovation paradigm. Knowledge sharing (KS) is a fundamental process for the emergence of communities of practice [11]. KS may result in more innovation, cost reduction, and standardization [12,13]. Such a strategy is mobilized in the worldwide Artificial Intelligence community with the website paperswithcode.com [14]¹, which capitalizes on and compares training datasets and artificial intelligence methods based on scientific articles. Therefore, sharing knowledge may be an effective lever to address the challenges related to the P2V DTp implementation. In this article, a web-based knowledge management system (KMS) that documents P2V DTp and related case studies is presented.

The article is organized as follows. The first section introduces background knowledge on DT implementation in general, on the physical to virtual twinning in particular, on knowledge sharing, and on affiliated web-based KMS. Then, a benchmark is conducted on existing KMSs documenting P2V DTp on the web. The benchmark criteria are based on the background section. Then, the proposed KMS, the *DT pipeline* platform, is presented. Its design methodology and main KM functionalities are described, followed

¹ The website does not longer exist.

49 by an illustration of the platform's use with an academic use case. The article concludes with a discussion on the limitations and
50 perspectives of the presented work, followed by a conclusion.

51 2 Background

52 2.1 Digital Twin, Digital Twin pipeline, and implementation challenges

53 The concept of DT emerged in the 2000s [4]. Its use has been documented in multiple sectors, including manufacturing, healthcare,
54 smart cities, maritime and shipping, aerospace, agriculture/farming, retail, and mining [6,7]. A DT addresses many application
55 purposes throughout a product or system lifecycle, including maintenance [15], production management, product design and
56 development [16], and product-service system functionalities [17].

57 DT implementation relies on technological bricks, also referred to as DT technologies, DT solutions, or DT tools. The main
58 technological bricks for the DT paradigm are IoT, cyber-physical systems, artificial intelligence, and cloud computing [7,8].
59 Semeraro et al. [6] proposed organizing the DT tools into three layers: the physical layer, which acquires data from the physical
60 twin; the network layer, which communicates data between the physical and virtual domains; and the computing layer, which
61 performs data processing operations. The DT tools can also be classified into functional categories. Qi et al. [18] classified DT tools
62 into five categories: "tools for cognizing and controlling physical world", such as sensors, actuators or IoT middleware; "tools for
63 digital modeling", *i.e.* geometric/physical/rule/behavioral modeling software; "tools for digital twin data management", *i.e.* tools
64 for data collection, transmission, storage, processing, fusion and visualization; "tools for digital twin service applications", *i.e.*
65 "platform tools, diagnosis and prognosis tools, simulation tools, optimization tools"; and "tools for connections in digital twin", *i.e.*
66 tools that enable "the communication, interaction, and exchange of information among physical entity, data center, service, and
67 virtual model". A given DT tool can be classified into multiple categories. For example, a software solution such as Dassault 3D
68 Experience [19] has been classified into subcategories of all five categories [18]. Moreover, the connectivity of all DT tools relies
69 on various communication protocols, at all levels of the automation pyramid [20] and through the Internet.

70 One way to visualize DT tool implementation is to consider a sequence of integrated components, either hardware or software,
71 through which data flows. Therefore, in this article, the concept of *digital twin pipeline* (DTp) is introduced. A DTp is defined as
72 an end-to-end solution composed of hardware and software elements, through which data is communicated or processed to
73 contribute to the DT application purposes. This concept encompasses systems that operate on data flowing from P2V, V2P, or V2V
74 in a DT. Therefore, DT tool implementation can be assimilated into the DTp design. The DTp functionalities can potentially address
75 multiple application purposes. For example, a DTp that acquires data from the production line through the machines' application
76 programming interfaces can contribute to predictive maintenance or production optimization. In this article, the meaning of the term
77 "digital twin pipeline" differs from other occurrences in the literature, such as the homonymous method for standardized DT
78 deployment [21] or a pipeline referring to an artefact implementation specification, *e.g.* in [22].

79 The DT's broad scope and the wide variety of DT tools pose implementation challenges, especially in small and medium enterprises.
80 The main challenges are related to i) the DT tools themselves, which might be too expensive or not mature enough, ii) the variety
81 of environmental conditions in which they may be deployed, such as production lines, cities, agricultural fields, or mobility, iii) the
82 relationships between components, where connectivity and security issues arise, iv) the lack of standards, regarding design
83 frameworks, architectures, modeling, performance measurement, or connectivity, and v) the wide range of skills needed, *e.g.* from
84 modeling to data acquisition, automation, network security, software development, data analysis, or physical system expertise.

85 As previously introduced, P2V DTp are fundamental systems for DT operation. The next section focuses on P2V DTp to identify
86 the current technologies and implementation challenges.

87 2.2 Physical-to-virtual Digital Twin pipeline

88 Based on the above DTp definition, a P2V DTp can be defined as a system that enables data communication from the physical to
89 the digital domain. Therefore, one end of the pipeline is necessarily a sensing element, such as a sensing machine element [23] or
90 an extension of the PT [10]. The second end of the P2V DTp can be located anywhere in the digital space. Setting the digital end of
91 a P2V DTp is not trivial due to the infinite nature of the digital space resulting from the interconnection of the software components.
92 This will be further discussed in section 5.

93 Therefore, a P2V DTp scope encompasses data acquisition systems (DAQ), subsystems that acquire data in programmable logic
94 controllers, distributed control systems, supervisory control and data acquisition systems, IoT sensor networks, RFID networks,
95 augmented-reality (AR) based human-machine interface systems (if the AR headset is used as a sensing element), any system
96 composed of DT tools, and sensing machine elements that enable a given data processing operation.

97 All these types of P2V DTp are composed of hardware and software DT tools from the three DT layers, as well as interoperability
98 standards, *i.e.* communication protocols and information structure standards, through and between the layers [6]. Table 1 exemplifies
99 a DT tool classification into the three layers, based on [6,24,25].

Table 1: Examples of DT tools classified according to the layer dimension and the materiality dimension,

Materiality/layer	Physical layer	Network layer	Computing layer
Hardware	Sensors DAQ hardware IoT sensors Data buses AR headset RFID Wireless sensor network (WSN)	Wi-Fi card Bluetooth card Dedicated network hardware	Servers Computing chips Processors Memory disks
Software	DAQ software Software program embedded in PLC CAD/CAM, CAE, MES, PDM, SCM, ERP as a source for product data	Application Programming Interface Middleware	Machine learning algorithm Modeling and simulation software
Interoperability standards	HART, Wireless HART ASi Profibus Interbus	MQTT OPC UA AutomationML Wireless communication protocols such as Wi-Fi, Bluetooth, or 4/5G	Functional Mock-up interface Other interoperability solutions

101

102 Despite the seemingly rigid nature of such a classification, a DT tool can play a role in several layers and therefore be classified into
 103 several layers. For example, a DAQ software can manage the data acquisition frequency, *i.e.* in the physical layer, can communicate
 104 data to other software, *i.e.* in the network layer, and can process data, such as digital signal conditioning or frequency analysis, *i.e.*
 105 in the computing layer.

106 From a P2V perspective, AR headsets appear only as sensors. However, with their V2P data visualization function, AR headsets
 107 can be classified as network hardware, as they serve as human-machine interface visualization hardware technologies.

108 The P2V DTp design challenges encompass the challenges related to the selection and implementation of each of these components,
 109 and their global integration. In this article, particular attention is paid to the sensor selection and integration for DT, which remains
 110 an ongoing research topic. Indeed, recent articles have identified that sensor selection and integration in DT have received little
 111 attention, and therefore, few systematic frameworks have emerged [10,26–28]. Husung et al. [10] proposed a systematic and iterative
 112 framework that considers the stakeholder objectives, the physical understanding of the system, and context-specific constraints such
 113 as disturbing factors. Fett et al. [26] also emphasize the specification of stakeholder objectives into technical requirements regarding
 114 the PT modeling, which is also the subject of ongoing research [29].

115 In addition to the lack of standards for DT implementation, P2V DTp design also faces well-known challenges such as connectivity
 116 between DT tools, security, and AI/big data management aspects [7,9,30,31]. Therefore, the wide variety of DT deployment
 117 scenarios and DT tools makes the P2V DTp design more difficult. Indeed, a DT can be designed from scratch or as an extension of
 118 an existing physical system [5], and design decisions address context-specific requirements related to environmental constraints and
 119 stakeholder application purposes.

120 This section introduced the wide scope of the P2V DTp, the related challenges, and some ongoing research. In the next section,
 121 some background on knowledge sharing is presented to show its relevance as a lever for DTp implementation and to support ongoing
 122 research.

123 2.3 Knowledge sharing

124 Nowadays, knowledge is seen as an important resource in organizational activities, whether for developing new products, choosing
 125 the right business strategy, or enhancing the capabilities of actors. Knowledge can be defined as meaningful informational content
 126 that enhances the capabilities of the actor who memorizes the knowledge. Knowledge management (KM) is the discipline that
 127 addresses the management aspects of such a resource [32]. One major activity of KM is knowledge sharing (KS), which aims to
 128 make explicit knowledge from one or several actors and make it available to others.

129 KS has demonstrated its major role in cost reduction, innovation, and the emergence of standards and communities of practice
 130 [11,12,33]. KS can be facilitated through face-to-face conversations, books, lectures, or via KM tools. The former mainly rely on
 131 information and communication technologies, such as wikis, forums, expert systems, blogs, or content management systems (CMS)
 132 [13,34]. The positive impact of KS mainly depends on trust, the governance of the media space, and the community culture
 133 [12,13,35–38].

134 Regarding the KS of P2V DTp design, the main actors potentially interested are academic and industrial. Academic actors may want
135 to share their research use cases or find documentation on existing P2V DTp. On the other hand, industrial actors may want to find
136 tailored operational solutions or share knowledge on P2V DTp as solutions vendors or in an open innovation mindset. Such a
137 community can be worldwide, with different expertise languages from various sectors. Moreover, knowledge on P2V DTp evolves
138 quickly due to the innovation of the DT tools and research advances in that field.

139 Therefore, considering the community characteristics and the DT implementation challenges, KS has good potential to support the
140 DT implementation if conducted with an appropriate KM approach. Given the worldwide community and the wide diversity of
141 knowledge to manage, the most appropriate KM approach seems to be a web-based KM tool enabling efficient knowledge capture,
142 knowledge organization, and knowledge search. In the next section, elements regarding web-based knowledge management systems
143 are presented.

144 2.4 Knowledge Management System

145 Knowledge sharing can be effectively supported through knowledge management tools. These tools facilitate knowledge capture
146 and enable the organization and search of capitalized knowledge [34]. KM tools are called knowledge management systems (KMS).
147 There are several types of KMSs on the web, including wikis, forums, CMSs (such as blogs), cloud-based document management
148 systems, and others [39]. The main activities of a KMS include knowledge capture, knowledge organization, knowledge search, and
149 authorization management.

150 Knowledge capture (KC) refers to the process of converting tacit knowledge from one actor into explicit knowledge in a knowledge
151 base. It corresponds to the knowledge externalization step in the model by [40]. Knowledge can be captured as unstructured content,
152 such as free text, or as structured content, for example, through a form with specific fields. In a document engineering approach, the
153 design of the document structure is a major step based on the analysis of the documented object and the information needs [41].
154 Several approaches exist to document a given topic or domain, or, in other words, to structure documentation. From a universal
155 framework perspective, facet analysis aims to describe a subject from several fundamental points of view [42]. Beau [43] proposed
156 a model with six foci: general, constitutive, functional, dynamic, individual, and critique. From an engineering perspective, product
157 knowledge representation is a central topic for the collaboration of various actors during the development phases [44]. Products are
158 often represented through their structure, functions, behavior, and requirements, such as with the Characteristics-Properties
159 Modelling approach [45] or the function-behavior-structure ontology [46,47] and one of its extended ontologies, Requirements-FBS
160 [48].

161 Knowledge organization (KO) aims to position knowledge contents in relation to each other [49]. Some KO approaches aim for
162 objective or universal classification, *e.g.* in scientific or librarian contexts. Other approaches allow domain-specific or user-view
163 classification [50]. Nowadays, ICT enables complex and dynamic KO through user collaboration. Some of the most well-known
164 collaborative KO approaches on websites are folksonomies (or collaborative tagging), ontologies, and faceted classification [42].
165 Collaborative KO can be considered as KC if the KO has value in itself.

166 Knowledge search (KSe) refers to the activity that aims to find targeted knowledge. On a website, the main strategies include
167 navigation between pages through meaningful hyperlinks or the use of a search engine with keywords, facets, or tags. Hyperlinks
168 can directly lead to related knowledge content, such as on Wikipedia, or to pages acting like a node in the knowledge map, such as
169 category pages listing many related contents. Therefore, the KSe efficiency strongly relies on the quality of the KC, KO, and KM
170 tools available to users.

171 Identity and access management (IAM) is a transversal aspect of a KMS. An appropriate IAM strategy is central for security,
172 governance, and collaboration aspects [51]. Indeed, it enables managing actions on content such as editing or reading. Different
173 access control strategies exist, with varying levels of granularity, ranging from simple authentication control to individually
174 personalized control.

175 Then, a domain analysis enables the identification of the knowledge of interest and the setting of the KMS requirements. The domain
176 analysis explores and identifies the users' information needs, their governance and collaboration culture, and the security
177 requirements.

178 In the background section, core elements of DT technologies and knowledge management were introduced. These elements
179 constitute the basis for the benchmark of existing KMSs presented in the next section.

180 3 Benchmark of DT solution-related knowledge management systems

181 This section presents a benchmark of existing community-based KMSs for P2V DTp. First, based on the background section, the
182 assessment criteria for the KMSs are established. Then, the KMS selection is presented. Finally, the assessment results are discussed.
183 A need for a KMS dedicated to P2V DTp documentation emerges from the results.

3.1 Assessment criteria

The KMS assessment criteria are grouped into two categories: the P2V DTp technologies criteria and the KM aspects criteria. The 18 criteria are illustrated in Figure 1.

As seen in the background sections 2.1 and 2.2, the P2V DTp scope encompasses the three DT layers [6], *i.e.* the physical, network, and computing layers. Moreover, the P2V DTp component types include hardware elements, software solutions, and communication protocols [18]. In the assessment, particular attention is paid to the knowledge about sensors, given the research gap previously presented. Therefore, the first nine criteria assess whether a KMS addresses i) sensors, ii) other hardware elements, iii) software solutions, iv) communication protocols, v) the physical layer, vi) the network layer, vii) the computing layer, viii) the implementation of all component types and layers at once, *i.e.* the P2V DTp scope, and ix) the former supported by real-world documented case studies. A tenth criterion is also added to assess whether x) a KMS documents complete DT case studies. A criterion is considered fulfilled if a substantial part of the KMS is dedicated to the assessed topic.

Regarding the KM aspects, as seen in the background sections 2.3 and 2.4, there are four functionalities to consider: KC, KO, KSe, and IAM. Therefore, eight more criteria are established. The KM criteria assess i) whether the knowledge is structured after the KC, ii) the KO approach, iii) the KSe strategies, and IAM openness aspects, *i.e.* whether there is open access to iv) read, v) publish, vi) modify, and vii) use the knowledge, and viii) whether there is a price barrier.

3.2 Selection

The search for existing P2V DTp KMSs was conducted across three solution groups.

The first group corresponds to the community forums of the main DT solution providers. This benchmark focuses on the manufacturing sector as it has the most DT solution vendors [6]. However, for other sectors such as health and building, vendors are often similar [6]. Based on the articles by Lehner et al. [52] and Semeraro et al. [6] and the authors' knowledge of the current market, the selected KMSs are: Siemens community [53], PTC community [54], Azure community [55], AWS community [56]², Eclipse Ditto GitHub examples [57], CtrlX Automation community [58], Ansys feed [59], 3DS community [60], and SAP community [61].

The second group of KMSs consists of the community forums of data acquisition (DAQ) solution providers. Indeed, these vendors are situated at the interface between sensors and digitalization. Therefore, DT implementation topics may emerge in such communities. Based on the authors' knowledge of the current market and the existence of brands' communities, the selected KMSs are the NI community [62] and the Dewesoft forum & support [63].

The third group of KMSs consists of the resource sections from the DT communities. Based on initiatives known to the authors and on web searches using the keywords "digital twin community", the selected KMSs are: the Industrial Digital Twin Association resources [64], the Digital Twin Consortium resources [65], and the Digital Twin Hub resources [66].

Regarding the criteria assessment in the forums, only the presence or absence of the P2V DTp in the channel nomenclature is assessed. Indeed, analyzing every message posted or every wiki page would exceed the granularity required for this benchmark. Moreover, the absence of a topic in a vendor forum does not necessarily mean that the vendor does not address it in its solution catalogue. Whereas, in the resources or case study repositories, the criteria assessment focuses on the component types addressed as well as their implementation granularity in the DT documentation.

² Nowadays <https://builder.aws.com>

219 The 14 KMSs are represented in the upper lines in Table 2. Moreover, the proposition of the article, the DT pipeline platform, is
 220 also assessed.

Figure 1: Assessment criteria for the KMSs benchmark

221 **3.3 Results**

222 The results of the assessment are displayed in Table 2. Results were retrieved on January 14, 2025, for the layers, component types,
 223 and IAM criteria, and on July 2, 2025, for the case study documentation, KC, KO, and KSe criteria. The acronym meanings are
 224 available in Table 3.

225 Table 2A: Assessment of DT solutions vendors KMS

Communities associated		Communities		Group 1: DT solutions vendors									
				Siemens community	PTC community	Azure community	AWS community	Eclipse ditto GitHub examples	CtrlX Automation community	Ansys feed (community)	3DS community	SAP community	
DT layers directly addressed	Physical layer	Y	N	N	N	Y	Y	N	N	N			
	network layer	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
	computing layer	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
Type of component of the DTp directly addressed	sensors/actuators	Y	N	N	N	Y	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N
	other hardware	Y	N	N	N	Y	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N
	software	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
All DT layers and types of DT components in one topic	communication protocols	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
	All DT layers and types of DT components in one topic, documented with a real-world case study	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
	Documentation of complete DT case studies	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
KM aspects	free	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
	open reading	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
	open publishing	CN	CN	CN	CN	CN	CN	CN	CN	CN	CN	CN	CN
	open editing	N	N	N	N	CN	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
	open use of the content	N	Y	N	Y	Y	N	N	N	N	N	N	N
Structure of knowledge	KO approach	US	US	US	US	US	US	US	US	US	US	US	US
	KSe strategies	HC ; Idx NavCat ; FS ; KW	HC ; Idx NavCat ; FS ; KW	HC ; Idx NavCat ; FS ; KW	Indexing KW	Free text NavTab	CatIdx FS ; KW	HC ; Idx NavCat ; FS ; KW	HC ; Idx NavCat ; FS ; KW				

226
 227 Table 2B: Assessment of DAQ vendors and DT communities KMS

Communities associated	Communities	Group 2: DAQ vendors		Group 3: DT communities			DT pipeline platform
		NI community	Dewesoft forum & support	Industrial Digital Twin Association website	Digital twin consortium resource	Digital twin hub resources	
DT layers directly addressed	Physical layer	Y	Y	N	N	N	Y
	network layer	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	Y
	computing layer	N	N	Y	Y	N	Y
Type of component of the DTp directly addressed	sensors/actuators	Y	Y	N	N	N	Y
	other hardware	Y	Y	N	N	N	Y
	software	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	Y
	communication protocols	Y	Y	Y	Y	N	Y
All DT layers and types of DT components in one topic		N	N	N	N	N	Y
All DT layers and types of DT components in one topic, documented with a real-world case study		N (limited to daq)	N	N	N	N	Y
Documentation of complete DT case studies		N	N	N	Y	Y	N
KM aspects	free	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
	open reading	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y	Y
	open publishing	CN	CN	N	N	N	CN
	open editing	N	N	N	N	N	CN
	open use of the content	Y	Y	Y	N	Y	Y
	Structuration of knowledge	US	US	mixed	US	US	Structured
	KO approach	HC ; Idx	HC	CatIdx	HC	CatIdx	FC
KSe search strategies	NavCat ; FS ; KW	NavCat ; KW	FS ; KW	NavTab	FS ; KW	NavCat ; FS ; KW ; LP	

228 Table 3: Benchmark acronym table

Y	Yes
N	No
CN	Connection Needed
US	Unstructured
HC	Hierarchical Category
Idx	Indexing
CatIdx	Categorized Indexing
FC	Faceted Classification
NavCat	Navigation through Categories
FS	Faceted Search
KW	Keywords
NavTab	Navigation through Tabs
LP	Linked Pages

229

230 Regarding the DT layers and the type of components addressed, the KMSs in the DT solution and the DAQ vendors' groups contain
231 information corresponding to the brand product portfolio, e.g. for PTC, network and computational layers, software, and
232 communication protocols. The KMSs in the DT community group mainly contain computing or macro information about DT. Only
233 the Siemens and CtrlX Automation communities met all the layers and component types criteria. Moreover, only the CtrlX
234 Automation community KMS has a dedicated space for P2V DTp implementation, i.e. the solution sets in the how-to section.

235 The documentation of real-world case studies is rarely addressed. Indeed, no satisfactory P2V DTp documentation was found.
236 However, 2 KMSs, both in the DT communities' group, document complete DT case studies, i.e. the Digital Twin Consortium and
237 the Digital Twin Hub resources.

238 Regarding IAM aspects, all the KMSs were free to use, and most of them allowed open reading. To publish content, the KMSs in
239 the DT solution and the DAQ vendors' groups required connected users, while the KMSs in the DT communities' group had a
240 closed publishing system. No editing option for existing knowledge was found in any of the KMSs. Finally, the legal property of
241 the content and use varied according to the legal terms of the KMSs.

242 In all KMSs, the knowledge structure was judged to be unstructured, except for one type of resource on the IDTA KMS, i.e. the
243 Solutions hubs. Finally, the KO approaches and the KSe strategies were classical ones, with respectively hierarchical categories,
244 indexing, or a hybrid of the two former approaches, and navigation through categories, faceted search, or keyword search.

245 To conclude this section, no KMS was found that documents real-world case studies of P2V DTp at the implementation level, and
246 with all types of components at all DT layers. Moreover, it is noteworthy that sensors, other hardware DT tools, and the physical
247 layer are rarely addressed in DT vendors' community forums, except for those that offer hardware in their solution catalogues.

248 4 Proposition

249 In the previous sections, the relevance of a KMS for P2V DTp documentation and the absence of an existing solution were
250 demonstrated. Therefore, this section introduces the article's proposition: a KMS called *DT pipeline*. In section 4.1, the KMS design
251 is introduced, *i.e.* the information architecture, KC, KO, KSe, and IAM/collaborative features. This design was implemented as a
252 web application in a wiki/CMS. Then, in section 4.2, the KMS use is illustrated with an academic P2V DTp use case.

253 4.1 Design

254 4.1.1 Design approach

255 To design the platform, the methodology by Garrett [67] was followed. This methodology is a top-down, user-centered approach.
256 The approach is decomposed into five steps, or "planes". Each new plane refines the previous one. The first plane is the "strategy
257 plane", where the objective and the user's needs are defined. The second plane is the "scope plane", where the functional
258 specifications and content requirements are established. The third plane is the "structure plane", where the interaction elements and
259 the information architecture are designed. The fourth plane is the "skeleton plane", where interfaces, navigation, and information
260 display are designed in low- and medium-level prototypes, respectively named zoning and wireframing. The fifth and last plane is
261 the "surface plane", where the visual and interactive aspects of the user interfaces are designed in a high-level prototype that enables
262 testing to avoid pain points in the use phase.

263 In the next subsections, the results of the first four planes are presented, following the KMS dimensions previously identified. The
264 results of the last plane, the "surface plane", are briefly discussed and can be found as open research data in a dedicated repository
265 [68].

266 4.1.2 Overview

267 A web platform called *DT pipeline* was designed. The platform aims to create and manage a collaborative knowledge base (KB) on
268 P2V DTp. Users can document their use cases through structured documentation supported by ergonomic interfaces. A P2V DTp
269 document contains a general description, the DTp component list, its functionalities, its application purposes, its environmental
270 context, its valued properties, a procedural implementation section, and a section for additional material. Then, the knowledge is
271 organized through a multi-view classification, which is dynamically enhanced by the community itself. The links between items are
272 described in the UML class diagram in Figure 2. Moreover, knowledge can be found through intuitive navigation interfaces, with
273 an advanced search engine based on the classification and the fields of the document, *e.g.* through function or environment facets,
274 and via a community forum that allows webpage mentions. The overall information architecture, *i.e.* the organization and navigation
275 schemes of the website [67], is represented in Figure 3. Finally, the platform follows the open-source philosophy, making all content
276 available for reading and downloading. Moreover, the platform enables users to choose the collaboration modalities for their
277 document. Regarding the IAM aspect, the access control follows an attribute-based access control (ABAC) strategy [51], *i.e.* a thin
278 control based on individual attributes. User identification can occur through an identity federation [51,69] for research and
279 education, eduGAIN®, or through a dedicated user account on the platform. The platform was designed following [67] approach
280 and a domain analysis. The design can be qualified as a hybrid between a faceted/multi-view/user-need-oriented classification tool
281 [42,43] and a wiki [70].

282 4.1.3 Knowledge capture

283 The platform's main objects are the P2V DTp use case documents. These documents are structured based on a domain analysis and
284 user information needs regarding P2V DTp implementation. The domain analysis conducted in the background section 2.2 enabled
285 the identification of the information needs. These include the system structure, *i.e.* DT tools and communication protocols, its
286 technical functionalities, its properties, the application purposes it addresses, the environmental conditions faced, and the
287 implementation instructions. A P2V DTp document contains a field for each of these information needs, as schematized in Figure
288 2.

Figure 2: UML class diagram of the DT pipeline platform

289 Most of the information is provided via the selection of corresponding items. This concerns the DTp components, functionalities,
 290 properties, application purposes, and environmental facets.

291 The structure field represents the DTp components list. It can be any DT tool or communication protocol listed in section 2.2. The
 292 component items refer to the exact reference on the market, whether hardware or software, or to the communication protocols.

293 The environmental facets represent environmental conditions in which a DTp or a component may be used. This facet encompasses
 294 external requirements, whether needs to be fulfilled or constraints to be faced, or more general descriptive aspects. Some examples
 295 of environmental facets are waterproof, outdoor, indoor, and natural light.

296 The application purposes field aims to document the objectives to which the DTp contributes. This field concerns DT application
 297 purposes, *e.g.* predictive maintenance or production optimization, and other objectives of the actors who implement the DTp, *e.g.*
 298 pedagogical or proof of concept.

299 The functionality field represents the technical functionalities fulfilled by the DTp. The P2V DTp functionality differs from the DT
 300 application purposes. Indeed, a P2V DTp cannot fulfill a DT application purpose by itself, as it requires V2P retroaction according
 301 to the DT definition. Moreover, a P2V DTp functionality can be described in terms of a lower level than DT application purposes,
 302 *e.g.* “temperature data acquisition” or “DAQ to DT middleware”.

303 The property field enables fine documentation of the DTp with valued properties, either quantitatively or qualitatively. The
 304 properties can be used to sort or filter DTp for efficient KSe. Properties can be directly selected when editing the DTp, or they can
 305 be inherited when selecting other facets. This aspect is further discussed in section 5.1.

306 The procedural instructions field is for the DTp implementation description, as well as for its use phase workflow. This field is
 307 crucial because it targets the need for operationalized knowledge.

308 A P2V DTp document also contains fields for a general description, images, additional material such as scientific papers, additional
 309 technical documentation such as a code repository link, and the author's declaration. Moreover, as further discussed in subsections
 310 4.1.4 and 4.1.5 below, the documents can be collaboratively organized into several categories to facilitate KSe.

311 The DTp documentation requires item selection, and therefore, the item's existence on the platform. Users can create any item
 312 needed to document a DTp if it does not already exist in the KB. The document structure of the other items can be deduced from
 313 Figure 2, which gives an overall view of the relation between the items and some user experience (UX) and user interface (UI)
 314 aspects.

315 4.1.4 Knowledge organization

Figure 3: Information architecture

316 The platform's KO workflow aims to collaboratively build multi-view and user-need-oriented classifications. All items are
 317 classified, except properties. DTp and components are classified via specific items, which are respectively the DTp categories and
 318 the component categories. DTp and components can be classified into several categories. This enables the coexistence of multiple
 319 points of view or expertise languages to classify a given entity.

320 DTp or component categories can be specified into subcategories or abstracted into upper categories. Environmental facets are also
 321 organized by items of their type. Indeed, such items can be more or less specific and can therefore be classified relative to each
 322 other. The same logic applies to the functionalities and application purposes items.

323 4.1.5 Knowledge search

324 The KSe efficiency relies on the KO quality and the KM tools made available to users. There are three main strategies to find
 325 knowledge: navigation through documents, use of the search engine, and navigation in the community forum.

326 Users can search for knowledge by navigating through different foci, which are represented by the facets that constitute the DTp
327 documents [43]. The categorization is the abstract/synthetic focus. The functionality facets are the functional focus. The application
328 purpose facets are the purpose-oriented focus. The environment facets are the contextual focus. And the components are the
329 constitutive focus. These foci aim to represent the constraints or needs of users when searching for knowledge, *e.g.* a specific
330 strategic target set by the organization, an already implemented DT tool in the organization, or a specific environmental context of
331 the PT.

332 The platform also has an advanced search engine that enables users to send complex requests. Users can search documents in the
333 KB based on keywords in the title or description, and with an advanced faceted analysis. The facet selection can be done in any
334 faceted field of the document. Users can select either a given item of a given facet, *e.g.* for a DTp search, select a component or a
335 given DTp category, or they can select a category and all its subcategories, *e.g.* for a component search, they can select the item
336 sensors and all its subcategories. Then, the results appear in a table with properties displayed in columns. Users can sort and filter
337 the results based on the property values. If the search engine cannot perform the filtering or processing that a user wishes, then the
338 search results can be downloaded in CSV format to enable users to perform more complex data processing. Users can also download
339 the entire KB in CSV or JSON format.

340 Finally, users can navigate the community forum and the Q&A channels. Users might find a question similar to theirs and an
341 appropriate answer that mentions items from the platform.

342 4.1.6 Openness, IAM, and collaboration

343 The platform aligns with the open-source philosophy. This openness choice is supported by the literature on the open innovation
344 paradigm and knowledge sharing, as seen in section 2.3, as well as the many open initiatives in the DT community [71–74]. The
345 platform is open access, so any users with an internet browser can access the knowledge in reading mode. Moreover, the shared
346 knowledge is under the CC-BY-SA license unless otherwise specified. Therefore, any user can download the KB and use it in
347 accordance with the license terms.

348 To contribute to the platform, users must be connected. The authentication can occur via the identity federation [51,69] for research
349 and education, eduGAIN®, or via a dedicated user account on the platform. Once connected, users can create or edit content if
350 authorized. The edit authorizations are set by the owners of the pages. Component and DTp documents are owned by the first author,
351 who can then decide the collaboration openness. The envisioned access control is a thin ABAC strategy. The owner can authorize
352 individuals or groups of individuals to edit the documents field by field, based on an individual attribute, *e.g.* in a given sector, in a
353 given university, etc.

354 Abstract items such as categories, application purposes, functionalities, or environmental facets are not subject to authoring rights
355 and therefore do not have a field for declared authors by default. They are the community's responsibility unless a user claims
356 ownership for legitimate reasons. Otherwise, any connected user can edit such item documentation.

357 Regarding the collaborative aspects, a page can be edited by only one user at a time, but conversational tools are available for users
358 who wish to discuss. Indeed, on the community forum, one channel per page is envisioned, so users can discuss its content. A
359 comment section is also available at the bottom of the page if the owner decides to activate it. Another collaborative editing tool is
360 the page history. The previous versions are saved and can be restored by the editors if needed.

361 4.1.7 Display and interfaces

362 User satisfaction is a key criterion for assessing the KMS quality. The UI/UX are important aspects. To decrease the risk of
363 information overload, a sober display was chosen, and the document information is divided into tabs. Moreover, navigation between
364 pages is intuitive via colored hyperlinks and button affordance layouts. Particular attention was paid to pain points when navigating
365 through pages or selecting items. The platform has a responsive interface. The display automatically adapts to the device screen,
366 whether a PC or a smartphone. UX prototyping [67] is useful for conducting tests and can be done with software solutions such as
367 Figma, Adobe XD, or Azure RP. The prototype was realized using Figma,³ and the data are available as research data [68].

368 4.2 Application of the concept and illustration with an academic DTp

369 4.2.1 Software solution: YesWiki

370 The prototyped platform was implemented in a wiki/CMS called YesWiki⁴. The native software solution fulfills many of the
371 requirements set in the UX design phase. Indeed, the native CMS enables users to create free text pages, create structured pages
372 through forms, connect pages with a selection module, display connected pages in a dedicated page, manage authorizations
373 individually or in a group-based approach for each page and all fields, have individual accounts, and other minor functionalities.
374 Moreover, the application is accessible to non-developers, the information architecture and document structures can be easily

³ <https://www.figma.com/>

⁴ <https://yeswiki.net/>

375 augmented from the front-end without development, and the code is open-source with an active community. Regarding the overall
 376 rendering of the platform, only the look and feel using the CSS sheet is personalized. The rendering is likely to evolve in the future
 377 based on user feedback. However, specific modules were developed, such as the hierarchical categories manager, the property
 378 inheritance, and the advanced search interface. The eduGAIN connection and the forum webpage mention functionalities are still
 379 under development. Following the open-source philosophy, the code will be shared in a GitHub repository. The link will be available
 380 in the aforementioned research data soon after the article's publication.

381 4.2.2 Illustration with a production line

382 In this section, the framework for sharing DTp implementation experience is presented, based on an academic use case. The use
 383 case DTp, illustrated in Figure 4, aims to detect a geometrical change in a production line using an AR headset. A remote server
 384 hosts the CAD geometry and its spatial coordinates in the production site. The headset runs the appropriate program with the related
 385 downloaded data. In the meantime, the operator calibrates the headset spatially using a QR code. Finally, the headset displays the
 386 3D geometry, allowing users to detect any geometrical changes, such as position, orientation, or internal geometrical changes.

387 The first page users will encounter is the home page. This page presents the platform's actualities, such as the newly posted DTp

Figure 4: Use case DTp, AR-based geometrical change detection

388 and components. From there, users can authenticate in the upper right of the screen or create an account. After creating an account,
 389 users are invited to create an individual page via the directory form. This enables users to add diverse information about themselves,
 390 such as the name of their organization or their location in the world. This will also enable users to declare themselves in the “declared
 391 author” fields of the DTp and the component documents.

392 Logged in or not, users can start navigating through the home page items or via the header. The header is on every webpage. As
 393 previously illustrated in Figure 3, it contains hyperlinks to the main navigation interfaces, *i.e.* tree view of the categories and facets,
 394 to the advanced search engine, and to the new item creation interfaces. To create a new DTp item, users can click on the link in the
 395 header.

396 These actions open the DTp form, allowing users to fill in the DTp title, the objectives, and add images. Then, users can select the
 397 DTp categories, components, application purposes, functionalities, and environmental facets through a keyword search bar or a
 398 category tree view. Users can further select additional properties if the relevant ones are not inherited, and fill in the property values.
 399 Finally, they can write the DTp implementation instructions, add additional material, select another DTp in the KB, *e.g.* previous
 400 versions or conceptual forks, and declare themselves as authors (see Fig. 5).

Title *

Title

Objectives ? *

Objectives

Image

Browse... No file selected

Categories

- Category of component
- Environmental facet
- Functionality
- Application purposes
- Category of DT pipeline

Properties

No corresponding property

Additional properties

Search

No corresponding property

Components

Elements available ?

Filter elements

Number of elements: 7

Component documents + Add all

- Temperature sensor XYZ
- Hololens 2
- MQTT protocol
- Microsoft Azure
- Physical QR code
- WiFi

Your list ?

Empty list

Remove all

Format - **B** **I** **U** **S** **≡** **-** **🔗** **📄** **📁** File Layout components - ?

Procedural description ?

Step 1 :

Format - **B** **I** **U** **S** **≡** **-** **🔗** **📄** **📁** File Layout components - ?

Complementary resources ?

File upload

Browse... No file selected

DT pipeline related

Elements available ?

Filter elements

Number of elements: 1

DT pipeline documents + Add all

- CAD model superposition with
Hololens 2 on a production line

Your list ?

Empty list

Remove all

Declared authors

- Jane Doe
- John Doe

Figure 5: DTp document template

402 Regarding the DTp use case, the raw information to be filled in is presented in

403 Table 4.

404 Table 4: Illustration - Raw information of the DTp

Field	Value
Title	CAD model superposition with HoloLens 2 on a production line
Objectives	This page aims to describe how to superpose a CAD model on its real-world twinned product. This pipeline was designed for a small production line.
Categories	AR-based system Production line Manufacturing sector
Components	Hololens 2 Microsoft azure

	Physical QR code WiFi Server model XYZ (hardware) MQTT protocol
Applications purposes	Geometrical coherence
Functionalities	AR visualization Human in the loop Orientation checking Position checking
Environmental facets	Changing daylight Indoor Wireless
Targeted property	Position precision (cm): 10cm Angular precision (°): 3° Recommended internet speed: 100 Mo/s, optical fiber Starting time: 5min Operation time: 2 minutes per machine Price: 3000-4000€ Operator skill needed: non-expert Deployment skill needed: medium
Additional material	Link to the git repository 2 Additional files
Related DTp	Comparison of a production line and its digital twin's geometry with a HoloLens
Declared authors	admin

405 The editing workflow is as follows.

406 Regarding the first fields, the title and objectives are limited to 200 and 500 characters, respectively, and the image has a 3:4 format
407 (see Figure 6).

408

Figure 6: DTp document, title, objectives, and image

409 To select the categories and facets, users can navigate through their tree views and check the corresponding boxes (see Figure 7).
410 The facet items must already exist before users fill in the field. Otherwise, users can save their DTp with a draft status, create the
411 missing item, and re-edit the DTp with the newly available item.

Categories

- ▶ Category of component
- ▼ **Environmental facet**
 - Changing day light
 - Dust proof
 - Indoor
 - Outdoor
- ▶ Temperature variation
- Waterproof
- White room
- Wireless
- Acidproof
- ▶ **Functionality**
- ▶ Application purposes
- ▶ **Category of DT pipeline**

Figure 7: DTp document, categories, and facets tree view

413 The category and facet selections induce property inheritance. Users can directly fill in the property values. Then, additional
 414 properties can be selected and their values can be filled in (see Figure 8).

415

Inherited properties

Position precision (cm)
10

Angular precision (°)
3

Recommended internet speed (Mo/s)
100

Starting time (min)
5

Operation time (min)
2 per machine

Operator skill needed
non-expert

Deployment skill needed
medium

Additional properties

Rechercher

Price ■
3000-4000€

.....

No other corresponding property

Figure 8: DTp document, properties

416 To select the components, users can use a keyword search interface (see Figure 9). The component items must already exist before
 417 users fill in the field. If a component does not exist, users can create a new one using the same logic as for the categories and facets.

Figure 9: DTp document, component selection

419 The next field is the procedural instructions section. Here, users are invited to share the DTp deployment instructions, as well as the
 420 use instructions. This field can be written using the Markdown language. For example, this supports users inserting hyperlinks,
 421 mentioning component webpages, or laying out the field with titles, lines, colors, or tables (see Figure 10).

422

423

Figure 10: DTp document, procedural instruction, as written and as displayed

424 Complementary resources can then be added. Users can add hyperlinks, upload files such as text, PDFs, or images, and display them
 425 using the Markdown language (see Figure 11).

Figure 11: DTp document, complementary resources, as written and as displayed

Then, users can highlight similarities or connections between their DT pipeline and others by selecting them (see Figure 12).

Figure 12: DTp document, selection of related DTp

Finally, users can add their name in the declared author field to be contacted by other users or for legal credits (see Figure 13).

Figure 13: DTp document, authorship declaration

Once users have submitted their form, the DTp document can be found in the KB and is displayed on the home page (see Figure 14).

Figure 14: Home page, new DTp document display

To find the document, users can navigate through the categories or facet documents (see Figure 15).

Production line

Description

This DT pipeline category aims to group the solutions related to production lines

Associated properties

- Operator Skill Level
- Deployment Skill Level
- Start-up Time
- Operation Time

Categories parents

- Category of DT pipeline

Categories enfants

- Assembly line
- Reconfigurable manufacturing system (RMS)

Related documents

- [CAD model superposition with Hololens 2 on a production line](#)

Figure 15: Category of DTp, related DTp display

436 Users can also find the document via the advanced search engine by selecting several items related to the DTp (see Figure 16a) and
437 using keywords (see Figure 16b).

438

Figure 16: Advanced search engine, a) facets selection, b) keyword search

439 Regarding the collaborative aspects, the original author of the DTp can set the editing rights for its document. By default, it is
440 accessible to all connected users (see Figure 17). The categorization fields should be open to editing so that the KO can be
441 collaborative. This enables other users to classify knowledge with their own language of expertise.

List of the page access rights ×

CadModelSuperpositionWithHololens2OnAPr

Reading rights (* for all, + identified user, @admins admin group):

*

Editing rights (* for all, + identified user, @admins admin group):

*

Change owner

admin ▼

Save
Cancel

Figure 17: DTp document, access control interface

443 The categories and facets can be collaboratively organized as well. In the category/facet document, users can select the children and
 444 the parents of the current item (see Figure 18, top part). The update is automatically reflected in the affiliated items. Users can also
 445 collaboratively assign properties to the categories or facets, so the DTp and components inherit them (see Figure 18, bottom part).

446 To conclude this section, the implemented platform fulfills many of the functionalities and requirements, *i.e.* structured documents,
 447 openness, collaborative aspects, IAM, and multi-view classifications. Although the interfaces are slightly different from the
 448 prototyped ones, the UX is similar. Moreover, YesWiki offers other functionalities to manage website page authorizations, action

Parents categories

- Category of component
 - Hardware
 - Sensors
 - Human Machine Interface Hardware
 - Data acquisition hardware
 - Memory
 - Communication protocols
 - Human Machine Interface
 - Software

Child categories

- Category of component
 - Hardware
 - Sensors
 - Augmented Reality sensors
 - Temperature sensors
 - Human Machine Interface Hardware
 - Data acquisition hardware
 - Memory
 - Communication protocols
 - Human Machine Interface
 - Software

Related properties

Rechercher

- Frequency

- Dimensions
- ⋮
- ⋮

Figure 18: Categories of components, a) parents and children selection, b) properties selection

449 authorizations, and user groups. The tool is also accessible to non-developers to manage and easily enhance the document structure,
 450 or create new forms and items.

5 Discussion

5.1 On DTp documentation

This article presents a tool that helps academic researchers, industrial users, and DT solution providers share knowledge about DT operationalization. The tool enables DT communities to access an up-to-date and multi-disciplinary portfolio of DT technologies, benchmarks of end-to-end DT solutions, *i.e.* DT pipelines, as well as insights into ongoing research and latest innovations.

The proposed KMS combines elements of the faceted classification (FC) approach [42,43] and wiki technology [70]. Indeed, regarding the FC, the platform supports collaborative, dynamic, and multi-view classification, as well as the description of an item through multiple foci, *i.e.* constitutive, functional, contextual, etc. The platform also shares similarities with wikis regarding open reading, collaborative editing, sober display, and navigation between pages via URLs. The high-level prototype can be found as research data in the following reference [68]. Moreover, the DTp document structure can be brought closer to the Function-Behavior-Structure ontology (FBS) [46] and its Requirement-FBS extension [48]. Both the FC and the FBS ontology have universal ambitions regarding the documentation of any topic and designed systems. Therefore, it can be assumed that the proposed KMS can be used to document V2P DTp and V2V DTp as well.

The P2V DTp documentation is supported by the KM tools with structured documents and collaborative FC fields. Still, even if the overall document structure is fixed, users have some degree of freedom when documenting their systems. As mentioned in the background section, the DTp digital end cannot be precisely defined. It mostly depends on the scope defined by the actors who describe their system. This flexibility enables them to document their system in a way that suits them best. The actors could even document their system in two distinct P2V DTp documents: the first being the data acquisition system (DAQ) only, with low-level functionality and global application purposes, and the second being the full system, including the DAQ and the data processing tools with higher-level functionalities and the same application purposes. Following the assumption previously made regarding the V2V DTp documentation, the actors could even create a DTp item dedicated to the integrated processing data DT tools, with the appropriate classification.

Documenting both DTp with generic or specific functionalities offers advantages. Indeed, on one hand, generic DTp enables actors to perform a wider benchmark for a given functionality of the P2V connection. This could also promote the transfer or inspiration of DTp between different sectors and contexts with similar environmental constraints. On the other hand, the existence of specific DTp enables actors to find solutions ready to be implemented for their problems.

The DTp documentation is also flexible regarding component selection. Indeed, if users do not wish to share the exact reference, they can select an abstract item related to the component category, *e.g.* the item “abstract temperature sensor” categorized under “temperature sensor”. However, it is recommended to share the exact reference to enable a more detailed description of the DTp via the component properties, and to emphasize the interoperability of the components in the instruction section of the DTp document.

Another aspect of the DTp documentation deserves to be discussed. Indeed, this process may promote the emergence of performance measurement standards. The inheritance of DTp properties through categories has been designed with this perspective in mind. Similar DTp likely share similar properties, which would promote documentation coherence, improve benchmarking efficiency, and potentially lead to measurement standards.

5.2 Limits

The work presented in this article has several limitations. Firstly, the proposed KMS has not been tested with a large community. Therefore, the collaboration efficiency remains theoretical and may require further empirical investigation. Similarly, the choice of the knowledge sharing strategy for P2V DTp documentation is based on theoretical investigation as well as similar initiatives in other sectors, such as the website paperswithcode.com [14].

Secondly, technical limitations can be identified based on the current platform design and implementation. The first limitation is that the component structure of the DTp document is simple. It only contains unordered and one-level lists, whether for components or facet items. This is a limitation regarding the potential complexity of the DTp structure or detailed functional analysis. Indeed, ordered and multi-level lists could be useful for modeling the structure of a DTp through subgroups of components, or for decomposing and rationally organizing the functionalities of the DTp.

Another documentation limitation is that the main facets are currently fixed. Other facets may emerge from the classification process and therefore might require their own field in the document, such as the sector or the PT type. However, the current features do not prevent such root categories from emerging. The implementation of such new facets can be the subject of future maintenance and continuous improvement operations. The YesWiki solution offers tools to facilitate such operations for admins.

The third limitation of the KMS is that it does not document case studies of complete digital twins. Indeed, documenting a DT would require integrating information on the PT itself or on the modeling process and data, which is not part of the proposed design. Moreover, the proposition was tested only with P2V DTp, and not with V2P or V2V DTp. Therefore, despite the previously

502 mentioned universal documenting approach, this aspect needs to be further experimented with and validated before working on
503 complete DT documentation.

504 Regarding the KO, challenges may arise with an increasing number of documents and items. A given category might classify many
505 items. Therefore, the classification might not fulfill its role, which is to distinguish items. The threshold for splitting a category into
506 subcategories is not known. Moreover, once a subcategory is created, some items may need to be reclassified. This work will rely
507 on the community's ability to judge whether the KO is good enough to support an efficient KSe. The open classification in the DTp
508 documents should enable users to reclassify the document if they identify a need.

509 Finally, the current biggest limit is the need for contributions to the platform. Indeed, the knowledge base on DTp, components, and
510 classifications must be collectively built. Therefore, the platform currently does not contain any DT implementation content.

511 5.3 Future works

512 The platform appears to have the potential to document more complex systems with a few more developments. Indeed, the FC and
513 FBS ontology can be used for any designed product, and by simply adding multi-level and ordered lists, a document can describe
514 complex systems and detailed functional analysis. Moreover, the simple possibility of adding a DTp in a DTp component list may
515 enable documenting complex DTp or even the complete implementation of a given DT in one document. As a general perspective,
516 the KMS could even be used to collaboratively document designed products that are not necessarily related to the DT paradigm,
517 using the appropriate classifications.

518 Moreover, after a substantial amount of contributions to the KMS, the open capitalized knowledge can be extracted and analyzed
519 using a case-based reasoning approach [75] to identify trends or the emergence of standards regarding performance measurement,
520 design approaches, sensor selection and integration, interoperability solutions, DT modeling, or DT implementation frameworks.
521 For example, regarding the sensor selection and integration challenges presented in section 2.2, the DTp document contains the
522 main information to consider [10,26,27]. Indeed, such information includes the stakeholders' objectives through the application
523 purposes facets, the requirements of the P2V system that can be deduced from the functionality and environmental facets, as well
524 as other context-specific attributes that can be described in the properties or categories of the DTp. Therefore, the documentation
525 enables detailed analysis of case studies, which might lead to the theorization of new sensor selection and integration frameworks
526 for DT.

527 Finally, workshops will be organized with DT experts to establish initial classifications/ontologies on the platform before its launch.
528 This will enable the identification of the root categories and create a reference regarding the classification granularity needed from
529 a DTp documentation perspective.

530 6 Conclusion

531 In this article, a web platform called the *DT pipeline* platform is presented. Background elements on DT technologies and knowledge
532 management systems were first developed. Then, a benchmark of existing knowledge sharing solutions for DT was performed, and
533 several limitations were identified. The *DT pipeline* platform was designed to document physical-to-virtual DT pipelines
534 collaboratively and to create an open knowledge base on the technologies supporting DT implementation, thereby overcoming the
535 limitations encountered in the benchmark. The knowledge management tools were selected based on the knowledge management
536 requirements and the knowledge sharing context. This design has been implemented in an open wiki/CMS, and its use was illustrated
537 with an academic DT pipeline. As the knowledge base grows, its value increases, and it can lead to the emergence of standards.
538 Now its future is mainly in the hands of the DT community.

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703 *Figure 19: Assessment criteria for the KMSs benchmark*

704 *Figure 20: UML class diagram of the DT pipeline platform*

705 *Figure 21: Information architecture*

706 *Figure 22: Use case DTp, AR-based geometrical change detection*

707 *Figure 23: DTp document template*

708 *Figure 24: DTp document, title, objectives, and image*

709 *Figure 25: DTp document, categories, and facets tree view*

710 *Figure 26: DTp document, properties*

711 *Figure 27: DTp document, component selection*

712 *Figure 28: DTp document, procedural instruction, as written and as displayed*

713 *Figure 29: DTp document, complementary resources, as written and as displayed*

714 *Figure 30: DTp document, selection of related DTp*

715 *Figure 31: DTp document, authorship declaration*

716 *Figure 32: Home page, new DTp document display*

717 *Figure 33: Category of DTp, related DTp display*

718 *Figure 34: Advanced search engine, a) facets selection, b) keyword search*

719 *Figure 35: DTp document, access control interface*

720 *Figure 36: Categories of components, a) parents and children selection, b) properties selection*

721

- 722 *Table 5: Examples of DT tools classified according to the layer dimension and the materiality dimension,*
- 723 *Table 6A: Assessment of DT solutions vendors KMS*
- 724 *Table 7B Assessment of DT solutions vendors KMS*
- 725 *Table 8: Benchmark acronym table*
- 726 *Table 9: Illustration - Raw information of the DTp*